

Socio-demographic Characteristics and Client Care Satisfaction among Older-Adult Admitted in The Two Tertiary Hospitals in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated socio-demographic characteristics and client care satisfaction among older- adult admitted in the two tertiary hospitals in Osun state, Nigeria. The study specifically examined the relationship between caring behaviour of nurses and clients' care satisfaction; and the effect of socio- demographic characteristics on clients' care satisfaction. The study employed a descriptive research design using two hypotheses. The population for the study were older adults admitted in the two tertiary hospitals in Osun State. A total number of one hundred and seventy-seven (177) respondents were selected from the two hospitals. A self-developed questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents. The face and content validity of the instrument was validated by experts in the field of Tests & Measurement. Reliability of the instrument was ascertained through Cronbach's Alpha and Cronbach's alpha value of 0.802 was gotten. Inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics and Chi-square were used to analyse the two stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that the caring behaviour of nurses was positively related to patients care satisfaction while socio-demographic characteristics such as gender, period of admission and age were correlates of patients care satisfaction. It was recommended among others that Nurses should be more active in patients' care by developing active listening skills and sensitive to patients' needs.

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Introduction

The global population of human beings aged 60 years and above is building up at an unprecedented rate with the pace more pronounced in the developing countries (United Nations, 2017). According to a 2018 report by World Health Organization, by year 2050, an estimated 22% of the world population will be 60 years or older, compared to 14 % today, and 8 % back in 1950. The United Nations also projects that by 2050, 75% of the world's population aged 60 and above will be living in the developing countries (United Nations, 2017). Nigeria as a developing country is not left out of this rising future demographic development, it ranks 24th globally among countries with highest proportion of older persons (Hirsch, Winters, Clarke & Ste-Marie, 2017), with older adult projected population growth rate of 3.2% (Population Reference Bureau, 2017), a rate that has been estimated to double by 2050 (Mbah, 2016). This trend calls for concern as it poses major economic, psychological, health, and social challenges to the Nigerian state. The main factors responsible for this changing pattern of population ageing are declining fertility and increasing longevity (United Nations, 2017). With increasing age, numerous underlying physiological changes occur, and the risk for older adults developing diseases and care dependency increases (World Health Organization, 2018).

It is estimated that 90% of adults over 65years experiences one or more chronic condition and need specific treatments and medical care, setting them apart from the rest of the population (Rural Health Information Hub, 2019). Older adults' patients have special needs for the delivery of their healthcare (Wilson, 2018). This is mainly due to the characteristic makeup found in this age group, their health status and their various misconceptions about illness and diseases. Older adults, once they are admitted to hospital wards are at an increased risk of poor outcome such as functional decline, increased length of hospital stay and iatrogenic complication. As a result of this complex health status, they require unique and specialize nursing care to promote their health and enhance their care satisfaction. Also in today's consumer-oriented health care markets, patient care satisfaction is a major component of hospital quality management systems (De Simone, Planta & Cicotto, 2018). Patient wants value for the money they spent in procuring quality care. Since the healthcare delivery system is a major contributor to the health and quality of life of older adult, their satisfaction with caring behaviour of nurses plays a major role in determining their quality of life.

Nurses' caring behaviour has a great impact on client-care satisfaction, the development of effective relationship with patient and influences the quality of life of patients. There is a clear interrelationship between caring behaviour of nurses and patient satisfaction with care (Abdullah, Kousar, Azhar, Waqas, & Gilani, 2017), the relationship is developed between the nurse and the patient which significantly influences care satisfaction. However, (Soliman, Kassam & Ibrahim, 2015) revealed a negative correlation between nurses' caring behaviour and patients' satisfaction. The satisfaction from caring behaviour of nurses is achieved when there is congruence between patient's expectation and the care they received (Vogus & McClelland, 2016). Older adults rated their satisfaction from caring behaviour of nurses as based on when there is affective comfort and compassion shown by nurses (Kathyrine, Calong, Gil, & Soriano, 2018). (Batbaatar, Dorjdagva, Luvsannyam, Savino & Amenta, 2017), identified the specific areas in which older adults express a high level of satisfaction with nursing care include interpersonal care, comfort, efficiency and competency.

Satisfaction with caring behaviour is highly essential in the field of health care (Naghnen, Tafreshi & Naderi, 2017) patients who are more satisfied with their care are more likely to comply to prescribed regimens and thus contributing to positive influence on health.

In measuring the level of patient satisfaction with nursing care is important to determine and evaluate whether patients' needs and expectations are met which can help nurses to plan appropriate nursing interventions for the patients (Darega, Dida, Letimo, Hunde, Hayile, Yeshitla & Amare, 2016). Also measuring patients' satisfaction with nursing care also could be effective in improving nursing service quality by facilitating the creation of standards for care (Batbaatar, et al., 2017).

In view of the above, the study investigated socio-demographic characteristics and client care satisfaction among older- adult admitted in the two tertiary hospitals in Osun state, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

1. the relationship between caring behaviour of nurses and clients' care satisfaction; and
2. the effect of socio- demographic characteristics on clients' care satisfaction

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were generated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between caring behaviour of nurses and clients' care satisfaction
2. There is no significant effect of socio- demographic characteristics on clients' care satisfaction

Methodology

A quantitative descriptive research design was used along with a structured questionnaire for the collection of data from patients in two Tertiary Hospitals in Osun State, Nigeria. They are: Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife, Osun State and Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo, Osun State. The study employed a descriptive research design using two hypotheses. The population for the study were older adults admitted in the two tertiary hospitals in Osun State. Purposive sampling technique was used to select respondents because of the mixed age of patients admitted into the various ward of the two hospitals used for the study using proportionate sampling technique. A total number of one hundred and seventy-seven (177) respondents were selected from the two hospitals.

A self-developed questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents. It consisted of three sections namely Section A, B and C. Section A sought for socio-demographic profile of the respondents such as age, gender, education qualification and days on admission by patients. Section B consisted of items on caring behaviour while Section C consisted of items on clients' care satisfaction. Both sections were measured on 4 point Likert scale. The face and content validity of the instrument was validated by experts in the field of Tests & Measurement. Reliability of the instrument was ascertained through Cronbach's Alpha and Cronbach's alpha value of 0.802 was gotten.

Data obtained from respondents were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. Inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics and Chi-square were used to analyse the two stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Presentation of Data

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage showing respondents' Demographic characteristics

SN	Variable	N = 177	
		Freq.	%
1	Gender	Male	87 49.2
		Female	90 50.8

		Total	177	100.0
2	Age	60-64yrs	78	44.1
		65-69yrs	24	13.6
		70-74yrs	15	8.5
		75-79yrs	42	23.7
		80yrs and above	18	10.2
		Total	177	100.0
		mean age = 64.7 ± 5.01(SD)		
3	Educ. Qualification	No formal Education	21	11.9
		Primary	15	8.5
		Secondary	57	32.2
		Tertiary	84	47.5
		Total	177	100.0
4	How long have you been on admission	2-5 days	51	28.8
		6-10 days	54	30.5
		11-15 days	33	18.6
		16-20 days	24	13.6
		20 days and above	15	8.5
		Total	177	100.0

Table 1 reveals the socio-demographic profile of the study population based on the gender, it revealed that majority (50.8%) of the respondents were female. The respondents were within 60 to 83 years' age range with a mean age of 64.7 ± 5.01(SD). The majority of the respondents (47.5%) had tertiary education while 30.5% has been on admission between 6 to 10days.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between caring behaviour of nurses and clients' care satisfaction

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment correlation showing the relationship between caring behaviour of nurses and care satisfaction

		Caring behaviour	Clients care satisfaction
Caring behaviour	Pearson Correlation	1	.718**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	177	177
Clients care satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.718**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	177	177

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 reveals the whether caring behaviour of nurses will be related to patients care satisfaction. A significant relationship existed between the independent variable and the criterion variable($r_{(175)} = .718, p = .000$). The null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant relationship between caring behaviour of nurses and clients' care satisfaction. The result shows that the caring behaviour of nurses is positively related to patients care satisfaction. The implication of this is that caring behaviour of nurses has good relationship with patients care satisfaction.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of socio- demographic characteristics on clients' care satisfaction

Table 3: The socio-demographic correlates of patient satisfaction

SN	Variable		N = 177				
			Freq.	%	X ²	Df	Sig
1	Gender	Male	87	49.2	57.213	3	.000
		Female	90	50.8			
		Total	177	100.0			
2	Age	60-64yrs	78	44.1	19.876	12	.011
		65-69yrs	24	13.6			
		70-74yrs	15	8.5			
		75-79yrs	42	23.7			
		80yrs above	18	10.2			
		Total	177	100.0			
3	Educ. Qualification	No formal Educ.	21	11.9	7.993	9	.233
		Primary	15	8.5			
		Secondary	57	32.2			
		Tertiary	84	47.5			
		Total	177	100.0			
4	How long have you been on admission	2-5 days	51	28.8	25.434	12	.000
		6-10 days	54	30.5			
		11-15 days	33	18.6			
		16-20 days	24	13.6			
		20 days above	15	8.5			
		Total	177	100.0			

Table 3 shows that the chi-square value obtained for gender is ($x^2 = 57.213$, $df = 3$, $p = .000$); period of admission ($x^2 = 25.434$, $df = 12$, $p = .000$); and age ($x^2 = 19.876$, $df = 12$, $p = .011$) at the significant levels of less than 0.05 for the three out of the variables respectively. Since these p -values were less than 0.05 values, it could be said that age, gender, and period of admission are correlates of patients care satisfaction. However, education status ($x^2 = 7.993$, $df = 9$, $p = .233$) is not a good correlate of patients care satisfaction.

Discussion

The socio-demographic profile of the study population based on the gender revealed that majority (50.8%) of the respondents were female. The respondents were within 60 to 83 years' age range with a mean age of 64.7 ± 5.01 (SD). The majority of the respondents (47.5%) had tertiary education; while 30.5% has been on admission between 6 to 10 years. The socio-demographic profile of the study population is similar to that of Batbaatar, *et al* (2017) who in their study reported that their respondents were Christians, Yoruba, had tertiary education and visited the hospitals more often. Also, it is similar to a study conducted in Abeokuta by Oredola and Odusanya (2017) which had more Christians and tertiary education.

The outcome of this study shows that there was significant relationship between caring behaviour of nurses and clients' care satisfaction. The implication of this is that caring behaviour of nurses has good relationship with patients care satisfaction. This supports the findings in the study by (Kathyrine, *et al*, 2018) that a significant relationship was noted between caring behaviour of nurses and patient satisfaction. Furthermore, studies by (Bucco, 2015, Kathyrine, *et al*., 2018) revealed that there is a direct relationship between patients' perception of caring and their level of satisfaction with care. Reck (2016) also reports that

there is a moderate relationship between patients' expectation and satisfaction, majority (58%) of the patients in the study were found to be highly satisfied with services provided. However, (Soliman, Kassam & Ibrahim, 2015) revealed a negative correlation between nurses' caring behaviour and patients' satisfaction.

The outcome of this study reveals that the following socio-demographic characteristics such as Gender, Period of admission and age are correlates of patients care satisfaction. This supports Soliman, Kassam and Ibrahim (2015) that female patients were more satisfied than males but there was no difference in the levels of satisfaction based on age and levels of education of the patients. However, this study reveals that education status is not a good correlates of patients care satisfaction.

Summary of Major Findings

The following are the major findings of the study:

1. There was significant relationship between caring behaviour of nurses and clients' care satisfaction.
2. Socio-demographic characteristics such as gender, period of admission and age were correlates of patients care satisfaction.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the caring behaviour of nurses was positively related to patients care satisfaction while socio-demographic characteristics such as gender, period of admission and age were correlates of patients care satisfaction.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Nurses should be more active in patients' care by developing active listening skills and sensitive to patients' needs.
2. There is a need to understand several unexplored aspects in the multifaceted area of caring, such as the factors influencing care rationing, nurses' critical thinking and decision-making processes, and the criteria used by nurses to allocate and distribute their resources among patients
3. Hospital management and policy makers should ensure adequate staffing and supply of equipment also to ensure conducive working environment for nurses in order to ensure that nurses deliver optimal care that will promote satisfaction among patients.

References

- Abdullah, S., Kousar, R., Azhar, M., Waqas, A., & Gilani, S. (2017). Nurses and patient perception regarding nurse caring behaviours and patients' satisfaction in Sri Ganga Ram hospital, Lahore. Pakistan. *International Annals of Medicine*, 1 (5) 1-8.
- Batbaatar, E., Dorjdagva, J., Luvsannyam, A., Mario- Savino, M., & Amenta, P. (2017). Determinants of Patient Satisfaction: A systematic review. Perspective in *Public Health Sage Journals*. <https://doi.org/19.1177/175.....>
- Bucco, T. (2015). The Relationship between Patients' Perception of Nurse Caring Behaviours, Nurses' Perception of Nurse Caring Behaviours and Patient Satisfaction in the Emergency Department. Seton Hall University. <https://doi.org/Scholarship.shu.edu/dissertations>.
- Darega, B., Dida, N., Letimo, T., Hunde, T., Hayile, Y., Yeshitla, S., & Amare, M. (2016). Perceived Quality of Nursing Care Practices in Inpatient Departments of Bale Zone Hospitals, Oromiya Regional State, Southeast Ethiopia. Facility -based cross sectional study. *Qual Prim Care*. 24(1):39-45.

- De Simone, S., Planta, A., Cicotto, G. (2018). The role of job satisfaction, work engagement, self-efficacy and agentic capacities on nurses' turnover intention and patient satisfaction. *Applied Nursing Research*, Elsevier <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnr>.
- Hirsch, J. A., Winters, M., Clarke, P. J., Ste-Marie, N. (2017) The influence of walkability on broader mobility for Canadian middle aged and older adults: An examination of Walk Score™ and the Mobility Over Varied ...*Journal of Preventive Medicine Science Direct*, Elsevier <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpmed>.
- Kathyrine, A., Calong, C., Gil, P., & Soriano, (2018). Caring Behaviour and Patient Satisfaction: Merging for Satisfaction *International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 11(2)
- Mbah, P. O. (2016). The Neoliberal State and Administrative reforms in Nigeria. *Afro Asian Journal of Social Science*, 7(2), 1-30.
- Naghneh, M. H. K., Tafreshi, M. Z., Naderi, M. (2017). The Relationship between Organizational commitment and nursing care behaviour.
- Rural Health Information Hub. (2019). Demographic changes and Ageing Population.
- Soliman, H. M., Kassam, A.H., & Ibrahim A. A. (2015). Correlation between patients' satisfaction and nurses caring behaviours. *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare* 5 (2), 56 - 67
- United Nations, Department of Economic and social Affairs, Population Division (2017). World Population Ageing.
- Vogus, T. J., McClelland, L. E. (2016). When the customer is the patient: Lessons from healthcare research on patient satisfaction and service quality ratings. *Human Resource Management Review* 26 (1),37-49.
- Wilson, C. K. (2018). Online Palliative Care Education in the skilled Nursing Facility. Viewed online via. Library.depaul.edu.
- World Health Organization (2018). Department of Ageing and Life – Course World Health Organization. Press Geneva Switzerland.

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